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Tech Connect Policy Workshop

Funded by
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INTRODUCTION

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TechConnect, funded under Horizon Europe, aims to inform and engage on reducing the gap between technology adoption and productivity with implications on policy development in the areas of work, skills development, and advanced technologies development.

Acting across hospital sites in four Member States, the project has to date completed over 600 hours of observations and interviews through 12 case studies on the deployment of technologies like AI and robotics.

Leading on from this rich and detailed ethnographic study, a policy workshop was convened on the 16th April 2026 that included the participation of the project partners, invited experts and advisors, and policy makers and actors from the European Commission and the OECD. The goal of the workshop was to translate the key findings of the project to date into policy-relevant conclusions and recommendations.

The following short paper provides a summary of the main outcomes of the discussions for reference.

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BACKGROUND

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Within the scope and context of TechConnect, the outcomes and initial findings have relevance for interventions across the defined pipeline of technology. This starts at development, procurement, deployment (i.e. introduction) through to operation.

On a European level, this area cuts across many strategies, policies and instruments that include the Digital Decade Policy Programme, Union of Skills, Apply AI strategy and the Quality Jobs Roadmap, among others.

Policies and their resulting instruments are regularly streamed into parallel fields that include education and training, innovation and industrial adoption, and technology excellence.

This is considered a limitation of the common mission to ensure that European industry and society has the competencies and capacities to develop and productively adopt advanced digital technologies to yield returns for both the worker and the adopting institution.

BACKGROUND

Additionally, the EU focus on equipping individuals with the right skills for the digital and green transitions remains necessary, but is no longer sufficient to ensure expected outcomes from technology. As an illustrative example, in the healthcare sector only 1 in 5 organisations reports full success in digital transformation initiatives. This despite having a highly trained and highly capable workforce.

Additionally, a third or fewer of SMEs using generative AI are taking measures to train staff, set internal guidelines, or research copyright, legal, and regulatory issues.[1]

OECD (2025), Generative AI and the SME Workforce: New Survey Evidence, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/2d08b99d-en>

The issue, therefore, is not that people lack skills, but that organisational, technical, and governance factors limit outcomes. For these reasons, this workshop introduced a view of instruments that considers whether they address the individual, the organisation or the system as a whole.

The workshop also introduced the concept of affordance gaps and bridging practices. Affordance gaps refer to the difference between the expected use and outcomes of a technology and the actual, while bridging practices define and uncover the, often hidden, working practices that occur from those persons and teams attempting to integrate a technology into their workflows.[2]

Hallin, A., Andersson, C., Uhlin, A., & Ivory, C. (2026). D2.2 Human-Technology Skills Complementarity Conceptual Framework II. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19254634>

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KEY POLICY MESSAGES

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INVESTING IN HUMANS AS DRIVERS OF SUCCESS

When advanced technologies are introduced to a system, disruption occurs on multiple levels. These disruptions affect role definition, communication lines and workflows.

The bridging practices that result form a necessary part of the adoption cycle and are inherently human skills and competences. Individuals often step in to ensure successful technology adoption by bridging the gaps that can occur between what a technology is expected to enable (intended affordances) and what it enables in practice (actual affordances).

Policies should recognise the value and necessity of these practices and the formalisation of new workflows, roles and processes as part of their incentivisation of technology adoption.

SYSTEM CAPABILITIES VS. INDIVIDUAL SKILLS

There is a need for greater focus on system-level policies and interventions rather than the more traditional but narrow focus on individual-level skills. The emphasis skills can be problematic for three reasons: 1. It can place an unfair burden on an individual to address what is a wider organisational or

[2] Hallin, A., Andersson, C., Uhlir, A., & Ivory, C. (2026). D2.2 Human-Technology Skills Complementarity Conceptual Framework II. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19254634>

KEY POLICY MESSAGES

sectoral challenge; 2. It can be a catchall term for a variety of causes, obscuring true barriers to effective technology uptake; 3. It is narrowing the fuller capacities required of an individual and an organisation to prove adaptability and navigate uncertainty and learning to learn.

The EU focus on skills ecosystems, lifelong learning systems, and resilience and competitiveness still tends to be operationalised through the lens of the individual learner. But digital transformations tend to succeed or fail at the level of integration, workflows, co-ordination and governance, that is, at the level of system architecture and

not just the user interface. Focusing on how organisations actually absorb and operationalise technology and addressing responsibility for technology and skills adoption at organisation and system level can therefore help to mitigate potential risks and increase the likelihood of success.

Organisations must be treated as a unit of Vocational and Educational Training (VET) policy by complementing skills policies with policies that support organisational capabilities, change management, workflow redesign and cross-functional coordination. This is particularly the case considering that persistent affordance gaps are rarely solvable at the same (often individual) level where they are first experienced or identified.

KEY POLICY MESSAGES

PROCUREMENT IS HINDERING NEW PRACTICES

Procurement regulations and the concern to ensure fair play and competition in the market generates hesitancy among organisations to fully engage with technology providers across all stages of the technology pipeline. This is especially significant in the public sector context, e.g. healthcare. Examples of potential solutions and mechanisms that could be availed of include modifications to a technology to improve workflow integration, or the participation in co-development relationships with technology suppliers.

Increased guidance on innovation procurement practices and revision of stringent legislation could further promote productive relationships between technology suppliers and public organisations. This could also lead to a rebalancing of the burden of risk between the two parties. At present, a hospital (for example) bears full responsibility for end stage operations before deployment, without clear visibility of outcomes, which leads to risk aversion.

KEY POLICY MESSAGES

FROM FRAGMENTATION TO PIPELINE THINKING

Increased policy co-ordination requires greater alignment across all stages of the technology adoption intervention pipeline, comprised of procurement, development, deployment and operation.

Policies related to the uptake of digital technologies and associated skills development should focus on each of these stages, be they in the area of education and training, industrial adoption or technology excellence.

It is important that instruments be aligned at EU level, for example linking

Digital Europe funding with VET and skills programmes, so that funding for technology and skills be connected. In this way, a more integrated approach that seeks to reduce fragmentation across the intervention pipeline can be developed.

The packaging of instruments is also key to achieving overall impact, and there are benefits to be gained by moving away from the KPIs of training and towards a greater emphasis on successful transformation and adoption of technologies by specific contexts.

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KEY DISCUSSION POINTS

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The overarching aim of the workshop discussion was to identify possible improvements in policies and practices on advanced digital skills and technology adoption, across intervention stages and levels.

DEVELOPMENT STAGE

EARLY END USER PERSPECTIVE

- Co-development of technology solutions can generate discomfort and uncertainty for public sector organisations, who do not wish to provide unfair advantage to any one provider.
- Developers therefore may not gain a full understanding of clients' requirements and the context in which the technology will operate.
- Technology developers must be assisted to focus on end users and understand the system perspective at an early stage if successful operation is to be ensured.
- The engagement in greater co-development relationships is encouraged to ensure that developers are aware of the context, workflows and limitations that define the successful deployment and operation of their solutions.

KEY DISCUSSION POINTS

PROCUREMENT STAGE

UNCERTAINTY AND RISK AVERSION

- Procurement stage is an appropriate intervention point at which to consider human-technology complementarity and whether the adoption of a particular digital technology will be sustainable.
- However, fear of vendor lock-in and uneasiness around the potential for breaches of public procurement and competition rules can hinder organisations from ensuring scope for necessary modifications and support from technology providers.

- Organisations must build in sufficient flexibility at procurement stage to allow for ongoing engagement with technology providers at later intervention stages.
- The provision of appropriate training for procurement professionals on what is legally permissible regarding ongoing engagement with suppliers throughout the intervention

TRAINING AND ENGAGEMENT AS A PREREQUISITE

- In many existing procurement processes, training and support for the use of a specific tool is considered but this is often quite limited in time and scope.

KEY DISCUSSION POINTS

- With a focus on pipeline thinking, public procurement rules could require that any procurement/deployment of digital systems in a publicly funded environment be accompanied by a 6-12 month training and implementation plan with a dedicated budget for coaching, peer learning and workflow adaptation.
- There should also be scope for further engagement with technology providers once any affordance gaps and bridging practices become apparent, as outlined above.

BALANCE OF RISKS FOR PUBLIC SECTOR CLIENTS

- Currently, there is a perceived imbalance in the risk ownership of a specific technology, with issues that become apparent at operation stage falling under the exclusive purview of the public sector client.
- There is a need to share the burden for successful technology adoption more equally between the public sector client and technology developers.
- One way to do this may be through the use of tailored KPIs, with organisations ensuring that any KPIs introduced in contracts be designed in such a way as to capture impact and performance at operation stage.

KEY DISCUSSION POINTS

DEPLOYMENT STAGE

ROLE SHIFTS

- When a new technology is introduced, roles are transformed. This can result in one role assuming authority and responsibility previously held by another. This generates uncertainty in accountability and brings roles into direct contact where this was not previously the case.
- Bridging practices occur that risk creating parallel channels or unauthorised workarounds, drawing in potential conflict between roles and undermining initial intended affordance of a solution.
- Organisations need to account and monitor for this to provide the required clarity to teams and individuals through comprehensive mapping of skills and roles within an organisation to mitigate against unintended impacts at operation stage.
- Policies emphasising the cross-functional nature of training programmes in the context of organisational supports should be considered.
- Organisations must also account for various levels at deployment stage. Supporting managers in recognising new practices, communicating purpose, responding to feedback, and translating processes is seen as a potential accelerant for successful digital adoption alongside training for teams and users.

KEY DISCUSSION POINTS

OPERATION STAGE

BRIDGING PRACTICES

- Bridging practices tend to emerge in organisations when a new technology is introduced as users find ways to make technologies workable. These can include workarounds, use of tacit knowledge and informal learning.
- While they sit at the interface of human and digital skills, the skills underpinning bridging practices are inherently human skills, covering areas such as creativity and adaptability. Bridging practices serve as crucial enablers of technology adoption as they

connect the existing skills of the workforce with new digital tools, thus ensuring that people and technology remain complementary.

- As such, bridging practices should be valued by organisations and harnessed in support of technology adoption objectives.
- One example of how this occurs is when superusers or technology enthusiasts emerge in organisations. These superusers or workplace learning facilitators play a valuable role in promoting and championing the uptake of technologies – helping teams to adapt, troubleshoot and learn in real time. Organisations should ensure that they are formally supported through the use of protected time, tools and training.

KEY DISCUSSION POINTS

SYSTEM CAPABILITIES VS INDIVIDUAL SKILLS

- A focus on skills can place the burden of responsibility disproportionately on individuals, who will not have control over many factors impacting digital adoption.
 - Because digital transformation often requires organisational and cultural change, a focus on organisational system capabilities is needed to create an enabling environment.
 - Funding should focus on workplace transformation and not solely on training for individuals. For example, ESF+ or Erasmus+ funding could not only support training courses, but also –
- workplace transformation projects where organisations redesign workflows around new technologies.
- Organisations should consider what skills are needed to ensure the operation of a digital technology is in full compliance with any pre-existing obligations, e.g. relating to legal frameworks or patient safety.
 - There is also scope to explicitly recognise and fund hybrid roles – like clinical informatics leads, digital coordinators or superusers through micro-credentials or dedicated training pathways.
 - Organisations should ensure that any KPIs introduced regarding the uptake of digital technologies be designed in such a way as to measure impact and organisational change – for example whether the system reduces duplication, improves workflows and is used as intended.

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CONCLUSIONS

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- Individuals employ bridging behaviours to make technology solutions work, using inherently human skills to do so. This is especially the case in contexts where there is a strong professional identity, such as in healthcare. Organisations must value and support this creativity and adaptability, while also ensuring that it is not required of individuals due to avoidable, organisation-level failures.
- Europe has built one of the most advanced skills policy frameworks in the world. But if we want digital transformation to actually deliver, we need to move from a focus on individual preparedness and whether people have the skills to use technology to a focus on

system performance and whether the system allows those skills to create value. By broadening responsibility for digital skills and adoption away from individuals to organisation and system levels, there will be greater scope to address the gaps and workarounds that can occur with technology adoption in a proactive manner.

- There is scope for increased policy coherence across the technology intervention pipeline in support of advanced digital skills and technology adoption. One way to achieve this would be for future funding instruments (such as the upcoming national and regional partnership plans) to focus on workplace transformation and general capacity-building in support of technology adoption, in tandem with the traditional area of education and training.

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